

Design for Values (DfV) in Action.

The case of Robotics for Social Sustainability

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Abstract— A plurality of methodologies and frameworks have been proposed in recent years to embed robotics and other emerging technologies in human social practices, in line with the policy-aims of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). In this paper, we discuss and explore recent findings related to Design for Values (DfV), which is a systematic and theoretically grounded approach that tries to integrate design processes with human social and moral values. Such findings will be analysed in light of robotic solutions and applications, and by discussing and reviewing some of the results we recently published. The main objective is to show how and to what extent DfV may constitute a coherent methodology to incorporate dimensions of social sustainability into robotic design and development. This may serve to further advance the understanding of robotics as an inherently cross-domain field of studies, as primarily laid out in the scientific mission of Robot Companions (RCs), i.e., robots that will be designed to create new sustainable, affordable, and socially beneficial solutions for all citizens.

Keywords—*Design for Values (DfV), Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Robot Companions (RCs), Social Sustainability*

I. INTRODUCTION

In those last years, the question of how and to what extent robots and other emerging technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) need to be embedded in human social practices and domains, and to be aligned with societal values and standards has sparked much controversy. Lively contemporary debates have also emerged in line with the aims of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), i.e. an approach related to science and innovation developed in the European Union policy environment, whose primary goal is to realise a “value alignment” of research and innovation activities and governance with beneficial and shared societal ends [1]. Following such approach, an extended and multifaceted branch of studies have tried to introduce participatory methods and tools into the work of science and innovation actors, in order to make them “mutually responsive to each other with a view to the (ethical) acceptability, sustainability and societal desirability of the innovation process and its marketable products”, as laid out in von Schomberg’s definition of RRI [2]. A plurality of methods and definitions have thus proliferated in RRI, but for the most part this literature tends to neglect that innovation practices are not only a site for praxis for designers and engineers, but fundamentally a site of socio-

political practices [3]. What is missing is a critical reflection on the meta-governance of innovation, namely on the values, norms and principles that shape and underpin policy action and design requirements – being those values either explicit or implicit, or also emergent – since technologies are not implemented in a *vacuum* but show a ‘normative criticality’, i.e., a feature that make them capable of challenging public and justice dimensions, and of involving ‘grand challenges’, global and urgent transformations in society [4; 5; 6; 7]. In this paper, we discuss the role that design choices can play in shaping the technology trajectories; we argue that rather than being merely self-questioning practices regarding values and preferences of individual societal actors, these design choices should be understood as public practices with clear normative commitments. In doing so, we explore recent findings related to Value Sensitive Design (VSD) or, as recently identified by scholars, Design for Values (DfV), i.e. a theoretically grounded approach to the design of technologies that in a systematic and principled way integrates human social and moral values in design processes [8; 9; 10]. These findings will then be discussed in light of recent social robotic platforms, with the objective to show how DfV may constitute a coherent methodology to incorporate dimensions of social sustainability into the overall implementation process of robots. An highly multidisciplinary approach to the design of robotic platforms was already implemented with the idea of bioinspired robotics that, combining bio-inspiration and bio-application, aimed at designing robots that safely interact with humans and the environment [see the pioneering works at The BioRobotics Institute of the Sant’Anna School of Advanced Studies, 11; 12]. The interaction of fields like engineering, biological sciences and medicine is essential to develop valuable (safe, efficient, acceptable) robotic platforms, but the exploration of the role of values in engineering design can equally be considered a crucial step in outlining strategies of Responsible Innovation. As we will demonstrate, value-sensitive or value-directed design models can indeed contribute to overcome the traditional idea of robotics, and to further advance the understanding of robotics as an inherently cross-domain field of studies involving normative dimensions and substantial societal challenges. Moreover, this idea of robotics as a multidisciplinary field was also one of the central tenets of the vision of Robot Companions (RCs) for citizens, robots that will be designed to create new sustainable, affordable, and societally embedded interactions with humans [13]. DfV as a method,

may serve to further advance the incremental approach inherent in the vision of Robot Companions (RCs), by seeking to understand emerging social processes and by integrating such human and social science analyses into science and engineering initiatives.

II. DESIGN FOR VALUES (DfV)

A. Origins and Methodology

Recent policy papers in Europe have expressed the need for the inclusion of human values and principles in the design and implementation of emerging technologies, *e.g.* the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI proposed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI, or the New European Innovation Agenda presented by the European Commission in July 2022 [14, 15]. However, approaches like VSD or DfV are not new: they were firstly implemented in the domain of computer science and information systems, but they have now attracted much consensus by various disciplines that seek to integrate societal concerns in socio-technical systems (STS), in different domains like health, urban design, and so on [10]. The STS we are referring to are an entanglement of social, technical, and institutional layers, and are based on an interactional understanding of technology, according to which society and technology co-shape and co-vary, and the understanding of societal structures – and of people and communities’ perspective involved in such structures – is necessary to inform the design of systems [16]. The DfV methodology implies three different investigations: (1) *conceptual*, which involve philosophical explorations of values and values trade-offs, and the identification of direct and indirect stakeholders; (2) *empirical*, which require qualitative or quantitative methods to assess stakeholders’ expectations and experiences; and (3) *technical*, which imply retrospective or proactive analysis of technological systems, with the aim to assess if such systems support the values identified in the first two investigations and operationalise them in design requirements [17]. These investigations are iterative, and leave the room open to DfV practitioners to select and integrate methods from social science methodologies in order to analyse the case-by-case peculiar context of applications. Among those methods, scholars include semi-structured interviews, values scenarios, integrated stakeholders’ analysis, and many others [18], especially dynamic and continuous methods tailored for monitoring and re-designing the innovation processes, to address the increasingly flexible character of technologies like robotics and Artificial Intelligence [19].

B. Expanding DfV

DfV has encountered some criticism due to its supposed lack of normative foundation. Indeed, values in DfV are specified as “what a person or group of people consider important in life” [20], thus as an approach DfV allows a broad and general evaluation of values depending on the specific cultural and social circumstances of stakeholders. This point can lead to the undue overlap between values and mere preferences [21]. Moreover, another potential issue in the application of DfV methodologies is that they often neglect power structures in accounting for values, since they do not seem to adopt a wide-angle perspective on broader and global infrastructural, economic and governmental processes [22]. Recently, a multi-tiered approach to DfV has been advanced, to better frame the question of the normative foundation and specification of values, and their social

sources [8; 9]. The multi-tiered approach has expanded the DfV methodology in two distinct but interrelated ways: (1) firstly, it combines DfV analysis on contextual values with other values that are specifically tailored to autonomous systems and should be respected as much as possible, *e.g.* the ones identified by the High-Level Expert Group on AI (fairness, autonomy, *etc.*); and (2) secondly, it also expand DfV with other values that can be considered high-order collective and shared valuable ends to be promoted as much as possible, which are identified in the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) settled out in the United Nations’ 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development [8; 9; 23]. This multi-tiered approach can thus be interpreted to approximate DfV methodologies towards practices that can meaningfully implement and realise social good, and that can shed light on how robotics and other autonomous emerging technologies intervene as an enabler and facilitator of sustainable development.

III. ROBOTICS FOR SOCIAL SUSTAINABILITY: DfV IN ACTION

Social robotic applications have now entered any kind of workplaces, public spaces and institutions. Social robotic studies are predominantly evolving as a cross-domain field of studies, that requires social science insights and other disciplines theories (*e.g.* psychology, medicine, cognitive science, *etc.*) to understand the complexity of social interaction between humans (individuals, group agents, institutions) and robots in specific contexts and environments [24]. This point is especially relevant in initiatives that require the understanding of the scientific mission of Robot Companions (RCs), whose multidisciplinary nature seek to address emerging social practices. Therefore, the systematic and methodologically principled approaches of value-sensitive and value-directed design models can enrich the field of social robotics, and, specifically, the vision of Robot Companions (RCs), since the former can fulfil the recent demands of RRI for a forward-looking approach to responsibility in innovation that can take into account grand societal challenges, and for normative requirements that *ex ante* assign accountable tasks to the work of innovation actors [25]. To better demonstrate this argument, we can now move on to analyse specific robotic platforms, albeit in a retrospective fashion, with the lens of a multi-tiered DfV methodology. This may serve to address how a value alignment with public values, such as the SDGs, can be promoted within design and innovation processes related to social robotics. For example, let consider the case of the “DustCart Robot”, a wheeled autonomous robot developed for door-to-door garbage collection and tested a few years ago in the small town of Peccioli, in Tuscany (See Fig.1) [26].

Fig. 1. The DustCart Robots in the experimentation area of Peccioli, image retrieved from [26].

Such robotic platforms, which deal with social services and urban applications, may encourage good social behaviour and expectations, as citizens were supposed to prepare the garbage properly separated at given times in given areas, and are directly motivated to support sustainable waste management and the ideal of sustainable cities and communities as identified in SDG #11. A methodology as DfV can help in this case to acknowledge the role of robotics within the framework of sustainable development, and to provide the operationalisation of values in norms and tangible design requirements that meet citizens' needs and interests, according to a value hierarchy approach [27], but also in terms that require attention to values that are tailored to autonomous systems and should be respected, such as nonmaleficence in robots' capabilities in executing a task, or situational fairness and explicability.

Another example comprises the numerous robotic applications that can be implemented to support the good health and well-being (SDG #3) of elderly people. In those scenarios of robotic platforms in elderly care, engineering and design methods need to proactively consider and integrate care values (e.g. responsiveness, trust) into their models, since those values have a pivotal role in shaping not only the human-human interaction and care relationship between care-givers and care-receivers in a specific social environment, but also the human-robot interaction with Robots that has to be Companions (RCs) in such environments and care relationships [28]. The "Robot-Era System" (see Fig.2), a multi-robotic system that was designed to interact with humans in urban areas and homes and to collaborate in a multiplicity of daily tasks [29], or other similar robotic platforms, can be evaluated using the framework of DfV in order to incrementally advance the vision of Robot Companions (RCs) for citizens. DfV method individuates specific social and moral values that are to be implemented in Robot Companions (RCs) design, and that are also to be monitored and promoted in the whole life cycle of those robots, including but not limited to: (1) the mitigation of the gap between social groups; (2) the promotion of social protection and cohesion; and (3) the reduction of vulnerability and inequalities, which are all a core concern of the concept of sustainability as laid out in the UN 2030 Agenda (see SDG #1.3). This last question of social protection is also closely intertwined with questions of human development and access to decent work (see SDG #8), which should be carefully assessed in the context of the structural transformations of the world of work brought about by robotics and automation. Robotic platforms can be now designed to autonomously perform quality control processes in industry, with the result that the roles of operators are shifted to those of supervisors of processes and the working conditions are totally transformed [30]. These processes in Industry 4.0 may lead to a redrawing of the boundaries of a given job, which now can require human operators to engage in a "collaborative displacement" with robotic platforms, in order to achieve work-related valuable outputs [31]. In all those situations, at stake is the conception of "social sustainability" and the modalities to reach and approximate such a sustainable pillar via the design of robotic platforms. A methodology as DfV beyond empirical and technical investigations may provide conceptual tools to better understand what it means *robotics for social sustainability*, namely what it means to integrate social sustainability aspects into robots design and development.

Fig. 2. The Robot-Era System, from left to right Oro, Coro and Doro, image retrieved from [29].

Social sustainability is just one of the three dimensions of sustainable development, which also comprises environmental and economic-related aspects [32]. Nonetheless, it is the most difficult dimension to incorporate into sustainability projects, since social issues are the consequence of competing values and values trade-offs, uncertain and unpredictable effects, and of profound social implications on many areas and domains of life [33]. Methodologies as DfV can promote the ideal of social sustainability as a fully integrated, process-oriented, continuous practice [34; 35], which can include the perspective of communities and individuals' values, as well as much broader normative structures related to global challenges and to matters of equity of access to health, work, infrastructures, and other key public services.

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